

Connecting Data Intelligently for Automated Discovery in Health

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

Data is doubling every two years as companies and organizations learn to make greater use of connected technologies, yet storage costs are reducing at a much slower rate. Health-care and medical research are amongst the largest sectors seeing a surge in the need to better track performance and increase medical care efficiency while reducing costs through shared resources for health care systems under increased pressure. Why should health organizations live in isolation when they can benefit from one another? How can organizations find insight from data that already exist or that are being collected by collaborators?

2. Aim

We introduce solutions that can be put in place with technology and standards that facilitate the semi- or fully-automated discover and exchange of data for efficient healthcare systems analysis and research outcomes.

3. Approach

Analytical insights start with high quality data that can be either augmentative or complementary to answering health problems. We show how cloud based data indexing for capturing and amplifying metadata via artificial intelligence can accelerate the data discovery process for greater integration and collaboration. Furthermore, we discuss our collaborative efforts in establishing new international standards with other large genomic and health research organizations to move towards more automated data exchanges that meet stringent governance regulations leading to big data exchanges that can take place in days or hours rather than months.

4. Conclusions

Our approach demonstrates that effective intelligent technologies can be designed to accelerate data discovery without compromising privacy, thereby revealing both internal but also external data for higher data use efficiency. Furthermore, by adopting automated data access terms, organizations can substantially speed up the process of data exchange leading to cost and time effective insights.

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5. Keywords

Data indexing, enhanced metadata, artificial intelligence, automated discovery, data privacy

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